

Insecurity, School Administration, Teachers Job Performance and Students Performance in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper assessed the impact of insecurity on school administration, teachers' job performance, and students' academic performance in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Secondary data were used in the paper. The data were collected from print and online publications. The paper established that insecurity in Nigeria affected school administration, teachers' job performance, and students' academics in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Based on these discoveries, the paper hereby recommended that the Nigerian government should develop the political will to fight all forms of insecurity in the country by addressing socio-economic problems causing insecurity across the country. All levels of government should invest in school security by providing security facilities in the schools. The government should employ competent, agile, and well-trained school security guards in all schools.

INTRODUCTION

Children who successfully complete ten years of Basic Education and pass the Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate Examination (JAISCE) and Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) are enrolled in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) programs. In order to prepare them for the workforce, wealth creation, and entrepreneurship, it consists of the following: (i) senior secondary education; (ii) higher education; and (iii) continuing education provided in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) to either Basic Education graduates who are not proceeding to Senior Secondary Schools or Senior Secondary graduates who are not proceeding to the tertiary level (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013).

The objectives of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) are to: provide holders of the Basic Education Certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate with opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background; offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles; provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades; provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development; develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage; inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; foster patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties in spite of our diversity; and raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour. The realization of the objectives of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) depends on peaceful and conducive environment.

The high degree of insecurity puts the administration of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria in jeopardy. The nation's social, political, and economic aspects are all being impacted by this. One of the industries most impacted by issues with insecurity is education. In Nigeria, Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) institutions seem to be the most frequently targeted educational establishments. Abdulganiyu (2022) noted that Bandits and Boko Haram members in several occasion have attacked Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Northern Nigeria while Ogunode & Chijindu, (2022); Ojewale & Onuoha (2022); Adams, Adedeji, Majekodun, Kehinde & Adams (2021) and Adejumo (2011) concluded that Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) institutions are affected by insecurity problems in the Southern part of Nigeria. It is based on this that this paper is aimed to assess the impact of insecurity on school administration, teachers; job performance and students' academic performance of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Concept of Insecurity

Ogunode, & Adanna, (2022) defined Insecurity is defined as a situation or incident that causes a person or organization to feel threatened and afraid, making it impossible for them to do any important tasks. According to Hassan (2014), insecurity is a bad emotion that includes, among other things, dread, anxiety, uncertainty, and injustice. An individual may experience dissatisfaction or insecurity when they are powerless to change a situation and must rely on the unreliable cooperation of others. Learning is threatened by insecurity. The teaching and learning activities of such schools are frequently impacted by the state of peace or conflict in the communities surrounding them. Insecurity, according to Best (2006), is a deteriorating state of conflict, threats to human security, and intense violence marked by fighting, injuries, deaths, etc. "The state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protection" is how Beland (2005) defines insecurity. It alludes to little or nonexistent safety from harm. According to Olamosu (2000), insecurity is a state or circumstance in which a problem's existence takes on a critical dimension to the point that the social unit, system, organization, or society's survival or existence is in jeopardy.

Concept of School Administration

Ogunode and Ahaotu (2021); and Ogunode, Ahaotu, and Obi (2021) define school administration as the organization of school input in a way that facilitates the successful achievement of the school's goals. Administration of the school According to Ogunode (2020a), Ogunode refers to the process of planning and allocating school resources to carry out educational programs and meet school objectives. The methodical placement, organization, and arrangement of material and human resources for the implementation of educational programs to accomplish the school's established objectives is known as school administration. According to Okereke (2008), managing a school includes overseeing the curriculum, instruction, pastoral care, assessment, evaluation, and testing. In addition, he listed the following as responsibilities of school administration: staff appraisal, resource allocation, costing and forward planning, communication, handling of conflicts, staff negotiation, bargaining, and use of the practical skills required to survive the organization's policies. Due to the complexity of these tasks, the right equipment and resources are needed to complete them quickly and successfully.

According to Akinwumi and Jayeoba (2004), school administration is the methodical and methodical use of human, material, and program resources that are made available for education to accomplish educational objectives. The process of establishing, maintaining, and growing educational institutions following their objectives involves applying administrative principles, techniques, and practices to schools. The objectives of school administration according to Ogunode and Emmanuel (2020) and Ogunode & Atiga (2021) include to: achieve the objectives of educational institutions, plan and organize

school activities, minimize educational waste in the institution, distribute scarce educational resources wisely to achieve the goals of the school, supervise the extracurricular activities of students in the school, and improve the professional development of both teaching and non-teaching staff. Ensuring that the various educational institutions are implemented as intended is the main goal of school administration. For all teaching and non-teaching staff to perform their jobs efficiently, school management makes sure they are properly supervised.

Concept of Teachers Job Performance

The degree to which instructors complete their jobs and assignments within the institution is referred to as their work performance. The degree to which a teacher fulfills their given duties in the classroom is referred to as their work performance (Zaifada, Olowonefa & Ogunode, 2023). One way to characterize teachers' work effectiveness is how involved they are in the day-to-day operations of the school. It is known as the indicator of a teacher's efficacy in respect to the duties that are required of them in the classroom. It is intended to evaluate how effectively a teacher performs their duties in terms of instruction, discipline, lesson planning, delivery, and dedication (Awodiji, 2018). The act or procedure through which instructors carry out their formal duties in the classroom is known as their "job performance." According to Ajilabi (2000), a teacher's job performance is their careful commitment to meeting standards both inside and outside of the classroom. The fulfillment of duties and responsibilities within educational institutions is the definition of a teacher's work performance (Josiah, Audu, and Ogunode, 2023). The tasks a teacher completes within a specific time in the educational system to accomplish organizational objectives is known as their "job performance" (Obilade as cited in Selamat & Tautig, 2013). According to Olabisi, Okolo, and Ogunode (2023), teacher job performance is the actualization of given obligations in a classroom setting.

Writing lecture notes, and lesson plans, organizing instrument materials, assigning tests and exams, grading, representing the school, extracurricular activities, and motivating students are all considered parts of a teacher's job performance, according to Zaifada et al. (2023). The activities and programs teachers implement in the classroom, as well as the degree to which the objectives are met, all contribute to their job performance as teachers. The degree to which instructors carry out their official duties in the classroom is known as their work performance. The ability of teachers to impart knowledge in the areas of emotional, psychomotor, and cognitive learning to their students is a crucial aspect of their work performance. The roles that teachers play in the classroom to replace the functions of parents are covered by their work performance.

Concept of Students Academic Performance

Ogunode & Josiah, (2023) defined The entire learning outcome that students receive from educational institutions, including the concepts, information, and social and communication skills they have learned throughout

and retained their studies, is referred to as their academic performance. All structured educational programs and the information on student or learner gains in a classroom setting as a result of academic activities are collectively referred to as academic performance. According to Foster and Young (2004), a student's academic achievement serves as a gauge for assessing their value and potential. Academic performance was defined by Abdul (2002) as the students' standing in the grade point average of the courses they took for their annual examination. In other words, it is the outcome of students' assessment through comprehensive, systematic, diagnostic, progressive, formative, summative and cumulative evaluation of what they had gone through in a school setting.

It is the primary emphasis of the entire academic achievement. Academic performance refers to the entirety of the information, abilities, and conduct that a student or learner obtains through structured assessments in educational establishments. According to Ogunode et al. (2023) and Ogunode & Edet (2023), academic performance can also be defined as the completion of a well-structured curriculum, the growth of abilities, and the acquisition of knowledge that would enable the learner to contribute to society. Ijaiya (2004) asserted that student academic performance refers to the standard which students should be able to know and be able to do. Oloyede (2008) classified students' assessment into three areas (i) cognitive (ii) affective and (iii) psychomotor. Academic assessments are usually the first kind. The third involves the development of motor abilities, while the second involves adaptation. Moreover, a student's academic performance is determined by their ability to learn, understand the material, and develop the social skills necessary to contribute to their community and become useful members of it.

METHODOLOGY

Secondary data were used by the researcher. Reputable international publications such as CEON, Elsevier, Hindawi, JSTOR, IEEE, LearnTechlib SAGE, Nebraska, and Springer are only a few of the sources from which the secondary data were sorted. To choose and evaluate the papers, journals, and abstracts that were used for the article, this effort performed content analysis. Only a few of the several papers that had something to do with the subject matter were ultimately used. The literature review allowed for the general development of the study, which was previously focused on theoretical and conceptual exploration. The content analysis approach was used to choose the pertinent content of the various literature connected to this study (Modified model of Ogunode & Ukozor 2022).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of Insecurity on School Administration

Insecurity in Nigeria especially the Northern and Southern part of Nigeria has affected school administration. This submission is confirmed by Akor, Musa & Ogunode (2021) who concluded that insecurity challenges in Nigeria has an impact on education, particularly on secondary public institutions. A steady and tranquil teaching and learning environment is the

foundation for effective school administration. Also Sadiq, Ahmadu, Yaba, Saidu, Oloyede, Bashir, Okeke, Ibrahim (2021) and Ogunode (2021b) noted that insecurity in educational institution created the state of fear or threat and lack peace which affected administrative functions. They went further to affirmed that a situation where both school administrators, teachers, non-teaching staff and students are in the state of fear no any meaningful academic activities can take place. Ogunode, Umeora & Olatunde-Aiyedun, (2022); Ogunode & Kolo (2021) and Human Rights Watch (2016) opined that another significant issue that Nigerian schools, particularly those in the north of the nation, are dealing with is the issue of insecurity. Effective management of the secondary education program in the nation has been impeded by insecurity. Numerous administrators, instructors, support personnel, and students have lost their lives in schools. A multitude of school officials, educators, paraprofessionals, and pupils have been kidnapped, and Boko Haram terrorists have destroyed endless facilities. The disruption of school programs has resulted from school closures in Northeast Nigeria. (Garba, Ogunode, Musa, & Ahmed 2022; Ameh, 2015).

Impact of Insecurity on Teachers Job Performance

The majority of post-basic education and career development (PBECD) programs in Nigeria are negatively impacted by teacher job performance due to insecurity, particularly in the country's north and south. Ojukwu (2017) attested to the fact that insecurity affected environment where teaching take place which directly affected teacher job performance in the educational institutions. Musa (2020) and Abdul (2020) and Muhammed & Ogunode(2022) acknowledged that the Northern States government's policy of closing schools in the event of an attack on any state's educational facilities poses a threat to the advancement of education and has a detrimental effect on both the performance of teachers and student attendance. Emmanuel (2018) and Wuyo (2021) maintained that For educators, students, and other important stakeholders, the fact that schools are inaccessible due to inherent risks continues to be a major obstacle. In the majority of schools that are attacked, the horrific experience alone is impossible to forget. As a result, both instructors and pupils are left feeling fearful and find it extremely difficult to return to school to complete their teaching responsibilities. Ogunode & Ahaotu, (2021) noted that The state government in Northern Nigeria has been closing schools for a long time in response to attacks on educational institutions within or near the state. This has resulted in an unstable academic calendar for various educational institutions throughout the states, with secondary schools being the most affected. Educational institutions follow a set academic calendar that outlines the terms, academic session, and weeks when classes will be in session. Syllables and a work schedule are included in the school calendar. The closure of schools results in educators not carrying out the academic calendar and programs of educational institutions in an adequate manner, which is detrimental to the advancement of education since it causes periodic disruptions to teaching, learning, and other academic activities. These school closure have affected

teacher's job performance in most states affected by insecurity problems in Nigeria (Jimada, undated; Protect Education Attack, 2020; Ogunode & Chijindu, 2022).

Impact of Insecurity on Students' Academic Performance

Insecurity has impacted the academic achievement of students in the majority of Nigeria's post-basic education and career development (PBECD) programs. Ibrahim (2013) said that internal student relocation in Nigeria is caused by insecurity, particularly in the country's north. The state of unrest has forced many children to leave their institutions. Students' administration in educational institutions across the nation is being impacted by insecurity. "Western Education is forbidden" is the moniker of Boko Haram, an organization that has made no secret of its strong anti-education stance. When a terrorist organization strikes a community, schools are often among their first targets. Oluwa (2014), in Ogunode, Godwin and Unoaku (2021) and Paul & Igwebuikwe, (2018) noted, that Increased numbers of internally displaced people, political, social, and economic upheavals, and sluggish economic growth are some effects of insecurity. All of the mentioned have a detrimental effect on the people who live in such unsafe places. Ogunode & Ukozor (2022a); Ogunode & Ukozor (2022); Ogunode, Ahmed, Gregory, Abubakar (2020); Sanni (2015) and Salami (2004) are in agreement that insecurity has effects on students' academic performance in schools across Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper assessed the impact of insecurity on school administration, teachers; job performance and students' academic performance of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. The paper established that insecurity in Nigeria affected school administration, teacher's job performance and students of academic in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Based on these discoveries, the paper hereby recommended that the Nigerian government should develop the political will to fight all forms of insecurity in the country by addressing socio-economic problems causing insecurity across the country. All level of government should invest on school security. Government should employ competent, agile and well trained school security guards in all schools.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Considering the researchers' own limited knowledge and skills, the researcher has come to the realization while producing this article that there are still numerous deficiencies in language, writing, and presentation style. As a result, the researcher anticipates helpful critiques and recommendations from a range of sources to ensure the piece is flawless.

REFERENCES

- Abdulganiyu, B. A. (2022) Insecurity Is A Threat To Education In Nigeria
<https://dailytrust.com/insecurity-is-a-threat-to-education-in-Nigeria/#:~:text=Insecurity%20in%20Nigeria%20is%20drastically,extraordinary%20measures%20to%20combat%20it>.
- Adams, O.T., Adedeji, M.S., Majekodun, O.A., Kehinde, B.R., & Adams, T.A. (2021) The Effects of Insecurity on School System (Secondary Schools) in Nigeria. In Ochigbo, Beetseh, and Abubakar ed., *Global Insecurities: Challenges and the ways forward*. 1st ed. Akure: Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria, 126- 136.
- Adejumo, A.A. (2011). The problems and challenges of insecurity in Nigeria.
http://newsdiaryonline.com/tok_security.html
- Ajelabi, I.D. (2000). *Indiscipline and Policy Implementation problem in Selecting Secondary Schools in Rivers State*. Unpublished M.ED.Thesis, University of Port Harcourt.
- Akinwumi, F. &Jayeoba, A. O. (2004). *Principles and Practice of Educational Management*. Ibadan: Bash-Moses Printing Co. 3.
- Akor A. I. Musa, A & Ogunode, N, J (2021) Causes, Forms and Consequences of Insecurity on Nigerian Educational System: Implications for Educational Managers. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (18), 262-272
- Ameh, J.(2015). Borno: Reps Seek re-opening of schools. Punch Newspaper. www.punch.com July 30
- Atiya, I. & Palwasha, J. (nd). Teacher's job performance: The role of motivation. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 72 - 92 . Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3dec/ad55f1c23fd2507466ab89f49e34bfb4ac.pdf> on 11/07/2019
- Audu E., I. & Ogunode N., J. (2021). An Investigation into Problems Facing Public Secondary School Administrators in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA)*, 2 (5),66-74
- Awodiji, O. A. (2018). Staff development policies, practices and lecturers' job performance in Nigerian and Pakistani universities. (Unpublished doctoral thesis). University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Best, S. G. (2006). *The Method of Conflict Resolution and Transformation in Shedrack Gaya*

Best (ed) *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa*. Ibadan: Spectrum Book Ltd.

- Beland, D. (2005). *The Political Construction of Collective Insecurity: From Moral Panic to Blame Avoidance and Organised Irresponsibility*. Center for European Studies Working Paper Series 126.
- Cambell J. P. (2015). *Management: An introduction and Nigerian Perspective*. Enugu: Precision Printers and Publishers.
- Emmanuel U., W. (2018) Security Challenges of Attacks on Schools in Nigeria: The Role of School Administrators, Staff, Parents and Students
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National policy on education. 4th ed. Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Foster, R. & Young, J. (2004). Leadership: Current themes from the Educational literature. *The C. A. P. Journal* 2(12), 29-30.
- Garba, A. G. Ogunode, N. J Musa, A. & Ahmed. I (2022) Effects of Insecurity on Tertiary Education in North-East Nigeria and Way Forward. *The Spanish Journal of Society and Sustainability.*, (2), 10-17
- Human Rights Watch (2016) *set the classroom on fire*.
[https://www.hrw.org/report/2016/04/11/theyset-classrooms-fire/attacks-education northeast Nigeria](https://www.hrw.org/report/2016/04/11/theyset-classrooms-fire/attacks-education-northeast-Nigeria)
- Hassan, M.B. (2014). Boko Haram insurgency and the spate of insecurity in Nigeria: Manifestation of governance crisis. *Journal of Research on Humanities and Social Science*,4,(18).
- Ibrahim, M. B. (2013). Security challenges in educational institutions: The way forward, a paper presented at the annual lecture of Zaria Education Development Association (ZEDA). On 27th December 2013.
- Ijaiya, N. Y. S. (2004). Agents of examination malpractice in Nigerian public examinations: The strongest links. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 5(1), 55-62.
- Jimada, M. J (undated).Insecurity and its effects on school administration Lindaikaji (2021) 33- year-old UNIBEN lecturer shot dead by gunmen

- <https://www.lindaikejisblog.com/2021/6/33-yearold-uniben-lecturer-shot-dead-by-gunmen.html>
- Muhammed, H. & Ogunode, N. J. (2022). Impact of insecurity on secondary school administration in North-West geo-political, Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(3),9-21
- Ogunode N. J. Ahmed, L. Deborah Gregory, D. Abubakar. L. (2020) Administration of Public Educational Institutions in Nigeria: Problem and suggestion. *European Scholar Journal (ESJ)* 1(3), 6-13
- Ogunode N. J., & Ukozor C. U (2022a). Insecurity Challenges and Higher Education in Nigeria. *Best Journal of Innovation In Science, Research And Development*, 2 (5),61-78
- Ogunode, N. J. ., & Josiah, H. F. (2023). Deployment of Instructional Materials in Basic Schools in Nigeria: Impact, Challenges and Implications for Decision Making By School Administrators. *International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education*, 2(1), 118- 127. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJISE/article/view/966>
- Ogunode N. J., Godwin A. N. & Unoaku, O. C. (2021). *Effects of insecurity on school administration in Nigeria*. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 13. Retrieved from <https://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/628/572>
- Ogunode, N. J. & Edet, I. N (2023). Students' Academic Performance in Schools. *AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies*, 01(08),81-92
- Ogunode N. J. & Kolo, F (2021) Effects of Insecurity on Basic education in Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied science*, 1(7),1-8.
- Ogunode, N. J, Umeora, M & Olatunde-Aiyedun, T.G (2022) Impact of Insecurity on Administration of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in South-East Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. *Spanish Journal of innovation and integrity*, (8), 56- 62
- Ogunode, N. J. & Adanna, C. M. (2022) Impact of Insecurity on Early Child Care Development and Education (ECCDE) Programme and Effective Counselling for Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, (9) , 11-19
- Ogunode, N, J. & Chijindu, O. E (2022) Implication of Sit At Home Order (Insecurity) on Basic Education in South-East Geo-Political Zone of

Nigeria. *Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History*, 03 (07), 21-29

- Ogunode, N. J & Ukozor C. U (2022) Implication of Insecurity on Higher Education in South-East Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria and Way Forward. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(7), 77-85
- Ogunode N. J., & Ukozor C. U (2022a). Insecurity Challenges and Higher Education in Nigeria. *Best Journal of Innovation In Science, Research And Development*, 2 (5),61-78
- Ogunode, N., J. & Ahaotu, G. N. (2021). The effects of incessant closure of schools on school administration in Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology* 1(4), 98-103 22.
- Ogunode, N., J. Ahaotu G. N. & Obi-E., U. (2021) Effects of insecurity on school administration in Nigeria. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*,13. 94-102 24.
- Ogunode N, J,. (2021b). Administration of public secondary schools in Nigeria: Problems and suggestions. *Central Asian Journal of social sciences and history* 02 (02). 90-102 25.
- Ogunode, N., J & Abashi, L. E. (2020). An investigation into the administrative challenges facing the administration of Universal Basic schools in Abaji Area Council of FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. *WORLDWIDE JOURNAL OF RESEARCH*, 1 (3), 27-39.
- Ogunode N., J. (2020a) Challenges confronting the administration of English Language program: Secondary school context in Nigeria. *Journal of Research and Innovation in Language*, 2, (2), 59-6009
- Ogunode, N. J. & Atiga, T. (2021). Educational administration in Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research* 2(6),10-24
- Ojukwu, M.O. (2017). *Effect of insecurity of school environment on the academic performance of secondary school students in Imo State*. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies* ISSN 2202-9478 5 (1); January 2017 Australian International Academic Centre, Australiadoi:10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.5n.1p.20 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.5n.1p.20>
- Ojewale, O. & Onuoha, F. (May 3, 2022).Violence in Nigeria’s southeast demand022)s a holistic response. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/527413-violence-in-nigeria-south-eastdemands-a-holistic-response.html>

- Olabisi, S. O., Okolo, M. M. & Ogunode N.J. (2023). Motivation, teachers' job performance and students' academic performance in post-basic education and career development (PBECD), Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6 (7), 42- 50.
- Olamosun, B (2000). *Crisis of Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Book Farm Publisher.
- Oloyede, O. A. (2008). Leadership strategies, discipline and student academic achievement in public and private secondary schools in Kwara State Nigeria. *Unpublished doctoral thesis, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria*.
- Okereke, C. (2008). Quality assurance in teacher selection among private secondary schools in Owerri municipal, Imo state for effective implementation of the UBE. *Journal of Curriculum Organization for Nigeria*, 37-44.
- Paul, A. J. N. & Igwebuikwe, F. K (2018) Security challenges and management strategies in public secondary schools in Aba Education Zone of Abia State. *Journal of Economics and Environmental Education*, 3(1), 95-104.
- Protect Education Attack, (2020). Global Coalition: Sourced online from GCPEA on 9TH July 2020
- Sadiq L, Ahmadu, S. M., Yaba, M.I., Saidu, I., Oloyede, C. A., Bashir M., Okeke, J. M., Ibrahim H. (2021). *School abduction endanger Education in the North*. Daily Trust Newspaper, 28/07/2021 from <https://dailytrust.com/school-abductions-endanger-education-in-north>
- Salami, A. A. (2004) Nigerian Student and Campus cults: Quest for Recognition. *The Polymath, Journal of the Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta*: 1(2). 75-87
- Sanni, O. B. (2015) Effects of Insecurity and challenges on females' education in Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social Issues*, 18(3)